

Reference conditions and modification factors for the standardization of nondestructive variables used in the evaluation of existing timber structures

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Abstract

The main objective of this paper is to define the reference conditions and to propose modification factors to standardize the variables recorded by different nondestructive techniques. This practice will make it possible to generate consistent practical data while developing a procedure for the standardization of timber structure assessment.

The nondestructive variables analyzed are: time of flight, natural frequency, pullout resistance, penetration depth and drill resistance. The factors which affect these variables are: moisture content, temperature, size/length and positioning of sensors and angle to the grain. Reference conditions are defined and equations and modifications factors are proposed to help in the evaluation of existing timber structures and decision making.

Keywords: modification factors, nondestructive techniques, time of flight, natural frequency, pullout resistance, penetration depth, drill resistance.

1 INTRODUCTION

The assessment of timber properties by means of nondestructive techniques (NDT) is not a new concept. After the fundamental hypotheses for wood had been suggested, the first research took place in the late 1950s, and since then good results have been achieved.

Research into the use of NDT in wood products has been carried out in different areas: the principles of techniques and factors affecting use, the characterization of wood and wood-based materials, the evaluation of forest materials for structural and nonstructural applications, hazard assessment of urban trees and the assessment of existing structures, etc.

Additionally, although much work has gone into developing industrial devices, it is clear that for in-situ assessment portable equipment must be used. Due to previous experiences, several portable devices are commercially available. The results recorded are not always comparable, due to the effects of different factors and the test methodologies used. Obviously, this data cannot be neglected and standardized test procedures and adjustment factors should be defined, in order to integrate results and compare conclusions.

The standardization process consists of the development of a common NDT procedure for the evaluation of structural timber properties. This process could be based on previous works (Íñiguez-González et al. 2013) and should include the following features:

- Compilation of nondestructive test results from different research groups and studies, taking into account the species studied and devices used;
- The creation of a standardized data sheet to compare results, based on the adjustment factors proposed;
- Standardized equations.

54

55 This paper therefore focuses on the second and third features.

56

57 The information for each specimen in the data sheet can be summarized in four parts: general
58 information, geometry, non-destructive values and mechanical test results. Figure 1 summarizes the
59 parts considered and the values recorded in each part.

60

61

62

Fig. 1.Recorded database values

63 Afterwards, different adjustment factors, such as those proposed in this research paper, should be
64 applied to the recorded values in order to correct them to reference values for moisture content,
65 temperature, effect of size/length, position of sensors/angle to the grain, etc.

66

67 Once values are unified, standardization equations can be proposed and conclusions obtained.

68

69 The aim of this paper is to define the reference conditions and to propose modification factors to
70 standardize the nondestructive variables recorded by different NDT, in order to gain uniform practical
71 data and to develop a procedure for the standardization of timber structure assessment.

72

73 2 BACKGROUND

74

75 NDT for timber assessment is based on the estimation of its main physical and mechanical properties.
76 These are bending modulus of elasticity, E , bending strength, f_m , and density, ρ . In most cases, the
77 assessment of existing structures is governed by bending properties, and they also make it possible to
78 derive other properties such as tension and compression strength parallel to the grain, as indicated in
79 the EN 384:2010 standard. Density is a physical property that is strongly related to compression
80 strength perpendicular to the grain and embedment strength for joint design.

81

82 The use of NDT for existing timber structures has to focus on the in situ estimation of the mechanical
83 properties of structural size timber pieces with their singularities. Although there is extensive research
84 experience in NDT applied to wood (small clear specimens) and new structural timber, the results and
85 conclusions of this are still difficult to extrapolate to cover the in-situ measurement and assessment of
86 existing structures.

87

88 2.1 Nondestructive variables

89

90 The following variables are usually measured for the *in situ* assessment of timber properties by means
91 of nondestructive techniques:

92

93 *Time of flight (or equivalent velocity)*

94 The propagation of stress waves through material can be used to estimate its mechanical properties,
95 mainly stiffness. Time of flight (TOF) or the equivalent velocity, is the main parameter measured.

96 Attenuation can also be recorded and is related to strength properties. Two types of waves are used:

97 sonic stress waves for frequencies within the audible range, and ultrasonic stress waves at frequencies
98 above 20 kHz.

99

100 Some commercial and portable devices used for timber are ultrasound-based: the Sylvatest Duo and
101 Trio (CBS-CBT, France/Switzerland) and the USLab (Agricef, Brazil); stress wave devices: the
102 Microsecond Timer (Fakopp, Hungary) and the Hitman Director ST300, (Fibre-gen, New Zealand).

103

104 *Natural frequency*

105 In this method timber pieces are made to vibrate longitudinally or transversely by means of an impact
106 in the corresponding direction. The vibration of the piece occurs primarily in the system Eigen

107 frequencies. These frequencies are related to the stiffness properties of the piece and its

108 dimensions/geometry. In the case of longitudinal vibration, it is also possible to obtain the equivalent
109 velocity of stress wave transmission.

110

111 Some commercial devices which measure longitudinal vibration frequency are: the Portable Lumber
112 Grader (Fakopp, Hungary), the Timber Grader MTG (Brookhuis Micro-Electronics, Holland) and the

113 Hitman HM200 (Fibre-gen, New Zealand); and transverse vibration frequency: the Model 340

114 Transverse Vibration E-Computer (Metriguard, USA).

115

116 *Pullout resistance*

117 The pullout resistance method consists of the measurement of the withdrawal force of a screw with a
118 known diameter inserted into a timber piece to a certain depth. This force is related to the density of

119 the timber. There is also some experience with nails, but the equipment usually used is the Screw

120 Withdrawal Resistance Meter - SWRM (Fakopp, Hungary).

121

122 *Penetration depth*

123 This method is based on a similar principle to that of material hardness measurement, and it consists of
124 measuring resistance to the penetration of a hard solid piece. The Pilodyn 6J Forest (Proceq,

125 Switzerland) is the equipment most commonly used. It measures the penetration depth of a 2.5 mm

126 diameter steel needle, which is shot into the wood with a constant energy (6 Joules). Penetration depth

127 is related to the timber density in the outer part of the piece of wood. Another portable device uses the

128 same principle, the Woodpecker Wood Integrity Tester (Profound, The Netherlands).

129

130 *Drill resistance*

131 This method mainly focuses on gathering data on the internal condition of timber members and trees.

132 It uses a small diameter drill (1.5-3.0 mm) to bore into timber members while measuring resistance to

133 penetration (energy consumed at constant velocity). Resistance to drilling is proportional to density, so

134 this device can also be used to estimate the density of timber pieces. The commercial devices

135 commonly used are: the Resistograph Rinntech (Rinntech, Germany) and the IML Resi (IML

136 Instrumenta Mechanik Labor, Germany).

137

138 2.2 Factors affecting nondestructive variables

139

140 Nondestructive tests are easy and quick to perform, but it is important to note that several factors

141 affect nondestructive variables. These factors can be divided into two categories, according to their

142 origin: factors resulting directly from the wood sample, such as moisture content, temperature, quality,
143 etc. and, on the other hand, factors relating to the test procedures and devices used, such as transducer
144 coupling, path length and the size and shape of the specimen.

145

146 *Moisture content*

147 The moisture content (MC) of timber depends on the hydrothermal conditions of the surrounding air.
148 In a normal dry condition inside a building the MC of timber is from 8 to 12 %; this is slightly higher,
149 10 to 16 %, if the building is close to the coast. MC can be measured with electrical resistance
150 equipment, according to the EN 13183-2:2002 standard. A reference value of 12% MC is usually
151 adopted. Under usual conditions the range of MC variation is about $\pm 4\%$ (12 \pm 4%).

152

153 The determination of the MC of timber is useful, not only to adjust the values of NDT variables, but
154 also to detect abnormally high values that can be a sign of internal deterioration (fungi or insects).

155

156 The effect of MC on velocity has been studied in 30 pieces of Spruce (100x140 to 100x220 mm cross
157 section and 2.8 to 4.4 m length), with a decrease in ultrasound wave velocity (Steinkamp BP-V) of
158 approximately 0.8% for every 1% increase in MC, and for a variation of MC in the range from 5 to
159 30% (Sandoz 1989). Another recent work determined the effect of moisture content on ultrasound
160 velocity, stress waves and longitudinal vibration by testing 26 pieces of Scots pine, *Pinus sylvestris* L.
161 (100x150 mm in cross section and 3.0 m length) for moisture content ranging from 21 to 12%. A
162 decrease in velocity of approximately 0.6% (in ultrasound and stress wave) and 0.7% (longitudinal
163 vibration) was deduced for each 1% increase in moisture content (Montero 2013).

164

165 The influence of MC on stress wave velocity has been studied in Douglas-fir (51x51 to 51x305 mm
166 cross section pieces 2.44 m long) over a range of MC from 34-126 % to dry conditions (Wang 2008).
167 Stress wave velocity increases as MC decreases throughout the whole moisture range studied. In the
168 interval from 20 to 12% MC the velocity decreases approx. 1.7% for each 1% increase in MC.

169

170 For ultrasound velocity, a correction factor with a decrease in velocity of 0.53% for each 1% increase
171 in moisture content (in the range below 28% moisture content) was proposed for spruce (Steiger
172 1996).

173

174 A correction factor equation was proposed for ultrasound velocity (Steinkamp BP7 45 kHz) in Parana
175 pine. This showed a decrease in velocity of 0.45% for each 1% increase in moisture content below
176 fiber saturation point (Gonçalves and Leme 2008).

177

178 For ultrasound (Sylvatest) and vibration technique (Viscan) data, correction factors with a decrease in
179 ultrasound velocity of 0.60%, a decrease in dynamic modulus of elasticity for vibration of 0.87% and
180 an increase in density of 0.42% for each 1% increase in moisture content in the range below 28%
181 moisture con-tent, were proposed for spruce (Unterswieser and Schickhofer 2010).

182

183 The influence of MC on penetration testing was studied in Douglas-fir species, and an increase of 0.19
184 mm was proposed for each 1% increase in MC for the Pilodyn 6J (Smith and Morrell 1986). A linear
185 relationship of penetration with moisture content below 30% was deduced, although it was not
186 significantly affected by moisture content above 30%. On the other hand, studies (Calderón 2012)
187 using methods of measuring moisture content closer to those used in this work and for the range of 8
188 to 18% MC, show that there is no clear relationship with penetration.

189

190 No published research results on the influence of MC on screw withdrawal resistance with SWRM and
191 on drill resistance were found.

192

193 *Temperature*

194 In general, the mechanical properties of wood decrease when it is heated and increase when it is
195 cooled. However, in the practical range from -10 to 50 °C the effect is negligible; for example, in

196 structural mechanical timber design it is assumed that the properties of timber do not change and are
197 not affected by temperature below 50 °C. Consequently, the effect on measured nondestructive
198 variables is very small.

199

200 The influence of temperature is generally less important than moisture content for stress wave
201 propagation in the range from 6 to 18% MC (Bucur 2006, Launnay and Gilleta 1998), and it is
202 negligible for local nondestructive variables such as pullout or drill resistance. The reference value is
203 20 °C.

204

205 An increase in temperature slightly reduces the velocity of ultrasound propagation. This effect
206 increases with increasing timber moisture content. The reduction of velocity is estimated at 0.07 to
207 0.08 % for each 1 °C rise in temperature, for 12% moisture content and below fiber saturation point
208 (Sandoz 1991). For ultrasound technique (Sylvatest) records, a correction factor was proposed of a
209 decrease in velocity of approx. 0.08 % for each 1 °C increase (12% MC), in the range of -20 to 60 °C
210 (Sandoz 1993). The same correction factor was proposed by Steiger in the range from 20 to 40 °C
211 (Steiger 1996).

212

213 An adjustment equation was proposed in the Wood Handbook (Forest Products Laboratory,
214 Kretschmann 2010) for the mechanical properties of clear wood, with a decrease of 0.2% MOE for a T
215 increase of 1°C, with no influence of T over MOR in the range of -26 to 66 °C. The same correction
216 factor of 0.2% MOE was proposed by Green at 12% MC in the same range (Green and Evans 2008).

217

218 No published research results on the influence of temperature on probing (Pilodyn), screw withdrawal
219 resistance with SWRM and drill resistance were found. However, it is reasonable to neglect its effect
220 here.

221

222 *Size/length*

223 The size effect may have an influence on some local nondestructive variables such as pullout
224 resistance and penetration depth, as a consequence of the sawn pattern and cross-section size of the
225 piece. In the case of large cross-sections, the outer wood of the cross-section usually has narrow rings,
226 and the direction of probe penetration is more radial than it is tangential. On the other hand, small or
227 narrow cross-section pieces may have juvenile wood in the outer part of cross-section, so that
228 tangential penetration is possible.

229

230 Wave velocity propagation is independent of frequency. But different commercial devices work at
231 different wave frequencies, and the means used to detect signal start and stop may differ. The result is
232 influenced by signal attenuation and therefore depends on the length and size of the piece. It is more
233 difficult to establish a reference value for the size and length factors.

234

235 Finally, the effect of variable cross-section on stress wave velocity determination has been studied in
236 some works (Divos et al. 2005).

237

238 Wave transmission velocity is theoretically independent of piece length or cross-section. However, it
239 is observed that with different devices, slightly smaller velocities are obtained when time of flight is
240 measured over longer distances. This may be due to differences in how each device measures the start
241 and end of time of flight. This is related to signal frequency and damping. In general it was found that
242 the influence of length is similar for stress waves and ultrasound.

243

244 This fall in velocity (Δv) may be expressed for each meter of increased length ($\Delta v/\Delta L$). Its value
245 depends on the species and grade of timber pieces. The lower the grade, the greater is its influence. A
246 study was developed to estimate the influence of length on velocity (Sylvatest Duo, at a frequency of
247 22 kHz) in 40 45x145 mm cross-section pieces of Scots pine sawn timber. Measurements were made
248 in the length range from 4.4 to 1.1 m (Íñiguez et al. 2008). The average velocity was 5834 m/s in clear
249 timber and 5350 m/s in knotty timber. Velocity decreases amounted to 68 m/s for each additional

250 meter of length for clear timber and 83 m/s for knotty timber. This fall in velocity has a linear
251 relationship with length, at least in the range from 1 to 4 m length.

252
253 The effect of size on the velocity of ultrasound propagation was observed in a study of 161 pieces with
254 8 different combinations of length and cross-section of Tali (*Erythrophleumivorense* A. Chev.,
255 *Erythrophleumsuaveolens* Brenan.) timber pieces (Arriaga et al. 2006). Length has more influence on
256 velocity than cross-section. For each additional meter of length the velocity decreases by
257 approximately 83 m/s.

258
259 Another work studied the influence of length in the range from 3 to 0.5 m in clear timber of Scots,
260 laricio and radiata pine using ultrasound equipment with a frequency of 30 kHz (Acuña et al. 2007).
261 Velocity decreases of 120 m/s in Scots pine, 109 m/s in Corsican pine and 182 m/s in radiata pine
262 were detected for each additional meter.

263
264 This effect was also observed in large cross-section pieces of Scots and laricio pine timber (Íñiguez
265 2007). In two groups of 60 Scots pine pieces (150x200x4592 and 200x250x5206 mm) a velocity
266 decrease of 70 m/s was observed for each additional meter in length. In two other groups of laricio
267 pine pieces (150x200x4061 and 200x250x5063 mm) the decrease in velocity amounted to 127 m/s.
268 This is equivalent to a velocity decrease ratio of 1.4 % in Scots pine and 2.6 % in laricio pine for each
269 additional meter.

270
271 According to the author's preliminary and yet-to-be published results, recent research shows a
272 variation in velocity of approximately 81 to 155 m/s for each additional meter, from 4 to 1 m length.
273 Tests were performed in structural timber pieces of four different coniferous species (laricio pine,
274 Scots pine, radiata pine and maritime pine) 90x140 mm in cross-section and 4 m in length.

275
276 The bending properties of sawn timber can be predicted by the dynamic analysis of vibration, and the
277 longitudinal and transverse vibration methods achieve similar levels of accuracy. However, from a
278 practical point of view it is simpler to measure longitudinal vibration. The longitudinal vibration
279 method requires a minimum ratio $L/h = 6$ (length of the piece/width of the cross section), whereas
280 transverse vibration testing needs a minimum ratio s/h (span/depth of cross-section) of approximately
281 15 to 20 (Tanaka et al. 1991, Divos 2005). Accordingly, shorter pieces can be tested by longitudinal
282 vibration.

283
284 In the case of longitudinal vibration it is possible to determine the velocity of the stress wave from
285 frequency and the length of the piece. Piece length has no influence on the velocity obtained by
286 longitudinal vibration.

287
288 *Positioning of sensors/angle to the grain*

289 This factor affects the measurement of time of flight (or the equivalent wave propagation velocity).
290 The best positioning of sensors for measurements is at each end of the piece, obtaining the velocity
291 parallel to the grain.

292
293 This is not possible in practice in existing structures because the ends of pieces are not accessible. It is
294 therefore common practice to take measurements at an angle to the grain, positioning the sensors on
295 opposing faces at the maximum possible distance or, in the central portion of a span, obtaining the
296 velocity for a certain angle. For frequent dimensions of timber pieces and cross-section slenderness
297 (width/thickness = 1-2) and length (length/depth of the beam = 17-22) the angle with respect to the
298 grain varies from approx. 2 to 6 °. In some situations only the lower face of the piece is accessible, and
299 in this case sensors are placed on the same face, obtaining velocity parallel to the grain but under
300 special conditions, Figure 2.

301

Fig. 2. Three different sensor positions: left) Parallel to the grain, end to end, middle,) inclined respecting the grain, face to opposite face, and (right) on the same face.

These velocity values were obtained in 80 150x200 mm cross-section 4 m long pieces of radiata pine (Íñiguez et al. 2008). The velocity parallel to the grain was $v_0 = 4859$ m/s, the velocity from face to opposite face over a length equal to 18 times piece thickness was $v_\alpha = 4744$ m/s ($\alpha = 2,38^\circ$). This fall in velocity is equivalent to a 1% fall in velocity for each 1° of slope to the grain. The velocity obtained by positioning the sensors on the same face over a length equal to 18 times the thickness was $v_{0s} = 4724$ m/s. The ratio $v_{0s}/v_0 = 0.972$.

The influence of angle to the grain in ultrasound velocity was studied for Spanish Scots pine, laricio pine and radiata pine (Acuña et al. 2007) with pieces of approx. 60x400x2000 mm. For an interval of 0° to 6° , the decrease in velocity for each 1° of slope to the grain was 1.49 % for Scots pine and 1.93 % for Corsican and radiata pine. These values are higher than previous findings.

If velocity is measured only using sensors in the lower face of the piece, these values should be divided by a factor of 0.972 to obtain the velocity v_0 .

3. STANDARDIZATION PROPOSAL

3.1 Reference conditions

The variables obtained by nondestructive measurements (velocity, frequency, depth penetration, etc.) should be adjusted to reference conditions of MC, temperature, size and measurement arrangements. The physical or mechanical property in question would then be estimated for the reference values.

On the other hand, it should be kept in mind that this adjustment to reference values could be done directly on the final estimated property (density, MOE or MOR), instead of applying the adjustment to predictor variables. It is obvious that both procedures should be consistent.

For example, as the Wood Handbook (Forest Products Laboratory, Kretschmann 2010) explains, wave velocity is a function of the modulus of elasticity and density. This velocity decreases with increasing temperature or moisture content in proportion to the influence of these variables on the modulus of elasticity and density. The velocity decreases slightly with increasing frequency and amplitude of vibration, although for most common applications this effect is too small to be significant. The species in question has no recognized independent effect on the velocity of wave propagation. Variability in velocity in wood is directly related to the variability of the modulus of elasticity and density.

339

340 The following reference conditions proposed:

341

342 *Moisture content*

343 12% moisture content of timber is proposed as reference value to correct the nondestructive
344 measurements (stress wave, ultrasound wave velocity and penetration depth). This value corresponds
345 to the target MC for coniferous timber in service class 1 according to Eurocode 5 (EN 1995-1-1:2004).
346 Service class 1 is characterized by a MC in the materials corresponding to a temperature of 20°C and a
347 relative humidity of the surrounding air only exceeding 65% for a few weeks per year.

348

349 *Temperature*

350 20°C is the reference value proposed in general, and according to the definition of mechanical
351 properties in Eurocode 5. But considering its low effect on nondestructive variables this correction
352 may be neglected in frequent variable conditions (-10 to 50°C).

353

354 *Size*

355 The effect of size is considered here in terms of length, and 2.7 m is the proposed reference length to
356 correct nondestructive measurements (stress wave and ultrasound wave velocity). This value is based
357 on standard bending test slenderness (span/depth = 18) and the reference depth for bending strength of
358 solid timber in Eurocode 5 (150 mm, $18 \cdot 150 = 2700$ mm). In practice length may usually be in the
359 range from 3 to 6 m, and considering the reference value of 2.7 m the maximum effect would be a 7%
360 variation in velocity.

361

362 *Sensor positioning*

363 The end to end positioning of sensors, measuring the velocity parallel to the grain, is the proposed
364 reference position of sensors and reference angle. In practice the angle may usually be in the range
365 from 2 to 6°, so the maximum effect would be a 6% variation in velocity.

366

367 **3.2 Modification factors**

368

369 In this section, equations and modification factors are proposed for the adjustment of ND variables to
370 reference conditions.

371

372 *Moisture content*

373 The reference velocity of stress wave propagation, v_{12} (referred to 12% MC) may be obtained by
374 equation 1, from velocity at H % MC, v_H ,

375

$$v_{12} = \frac{v_H}{1 - (H - 12)k_H} \quad (1)$$

376 Where k_H is the adjustment factor for MC obtained as the ratio between the linear variation of velocity
377 relative to MC (Δ velocity/ Δ MC) related to velocity at 12% MC. A preliminary value of 0.01 (1%
378 velocity decrease for every 1% MC increase) is proposed for this, as it is a common result in several
379 research works.

380

381 The reference depth penetration of the Pilodyn 6J Forest, P₁₂ (referred to 12% MC) may be obtained
382 by equation 2 from depth penetration at H %, P_H ,

383

$$P_{12} = \frac{P_H}{1 + (H - 12)k_p} \quad (2)$$

384 Where k_p is the adjustment factor for MC obtained as the ratio between the linear variation
385 (depth/MC) related to depth penetration at 12% MC. A preliminary value of 0.02 is proposed (approx.
386 2% depth penetration increase for every 1% MC increase) for this factor. There are other experiences
387 suggesting that its effect be neglected for practical purposes.

388

389 *Temperature*

390 The reference velocity of stress wave propagation, v_{20} (referred to 20 °C temperature) is obtained by
391 equation 3 from velocity at T °C temperature, v_T ,

392
$$v_{20} = \frac{v_T}{1 - (T - 20)k_T} \quad (3)$$

393 Where k_T is the adjustment factor for temperature obtained as the ratio between the linear variation of
394 velocity relative to temperature ($\Delta\text{velocity}/\Delta T$) related to velocity at 20 °C. This factor has been
395 obtained in several research works with a value close to 0.00075 (a 0.075% velocity decrease for every
396 1 °C temperature increase). In practice the temperature may usually be in the range from 5 to 35 °C,
397 and considering the reference value of 20 °C the maximum effect would be 1.12 % of variation in
398 velocity.

400 *Size/length*

401 The reference velocity of stress wave propagation, $v_{2.7}$ (referred to a reference length of 2.7 m) is
402 obtained by equation 4 from velocity at L length in m, v_L ,

403
$$v_{2.7} = \frac{v_L}{1 - (L - 2.7)k_L} \quad (4)$$

404 Where k_L is the adjustment factor for length obtained as the ratio between the linear variation of
405 velocity relative to length ($\Delta\text{velocity}/\Delta L$) related to velocity at reference length 2.7 m.

406 *Positioning of sensors/angle of the grain*

407 The reference velocity of stress wave propagation, v_0 (parallel to the grain and end to end) is obtained
408 by equation 5, from velocity angle α in sexagesimal degrees ($\alpha \leq 10^\circ$), v_α ,

410
$$v_0 = \frac{v_\alpha}{1 - \alpha k_\alpha} \quad (5)$$

411 Where k_α is the adjustment factor for angle obtained as the ratio between the linear variation of
412 velocity relative to angle ($\Delta\text{velocity}/\Delta\alpha$) related to velocity parallel to the grain and end to end. This
413 factor was obtained in several studies with a value close to 0.01 (a 1% velocity decrease for every
414 additional grade increase in angle deviation) for ultrasound waves (at 22 kHz).

415
416 Finally, if velocity is measured only using sensors in the lower face of the piece, these values should
417 be divided by a factor of 0.972 to obtain the velocity v_0 .

418
419 **4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS**

420
421 The following conclusions can be drawn from revision of the state of the art:

422
423 The effect of MC on velocity varies from 0.6 to 1% for every 1% increase in MC and a variation of
424 MC in the range from 5 to 30%. The authors propose a modification factor of 1% until specific
425 research into this takes place. The influence of MC on depth penetration is close to 2% increase for
426 every 1% MC increase. This effect for screw withdrawal resistance and drill resistance is not shown in
427 published works. Specific studies should be carried out.

428
429 The effect of temperature can be neglected under normal ambient conditions.

430
431 In structural timber sizes, the size effect may be limited to the length. Cross-section has no relevant
432 influence, because this is usually at least 10 or 12 times less than length. Furthermore, the influence of
433 length is limited to velocity obtained from time of flight, but it has no influence on velocity calculated
434 from natural frequency.

435

436 When the position of sensors is not at each end of the specimen, a modification factor for angle is
437 required. A value of 1% decrease in velocity for every additional grade increase in angle deviation
438 (ultrasound) is proposed. Specific studies should be undertaken on the other wave techniques.
439

440 Given the lack detected in the state of the art, research work compiling nondestructive testing values
441 measured in coniferous and deciduous species is being undertaken in Spain. This has the purpose of
442 collecting existing test results measured in raw material and existing structures with different devices
443 and procedures. A testing protocol has also been designed and proposed in order to make the results of
444 future nondestructive tests by different researchers comparable. Although this study does not yet
445 include sufficient material to propose a grading method of timber based on nondestructive testing
446 results, it does mark the route to this goal.
447

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